

CHOICE AND ADAPTATION OF PRAGMATIC STRATEGIES

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Abstract: Based on this, we believe that the above statements can be combined into a single macro speech act. After all, no matter how long his speech is, the intended communicative goal is the same. In this case, the basic meaning of what is said is not important, but what is important is the content hidden inside the discourse.

Key words: Pragmatics, strategy, implicature, rhetoric, performative.

The concept of strategy is often found in literature related to pragmatics. Pragmatic strategies refer to the use of language to achieve a specific goal. As noted by pragmalinguists, "Language strategy is the intersection of explicitness and implicitness in meaning-making, which occurs consciously and unconsciously in the context of sentences or discourse structures." These are manifested, for example, in speech implicature, politeness, irony and other forms. Strategies come into play in any type of communication context and are involved in the realization of various pragmatic goals.

Thus, speaking persons choose various strategies or rhetorical actions and make a plan to adapt the speech to meet the existing need and to ensure that the conversation takes place within the framework of etiquette. In addition, they want their speech behavior to be an alternative to the behavior of their interlocutors.

We will try to consider aspects related to the choice of strategy of phenomena such as speech acts, politeness and irony, which constitute rhetorical and interpersonal aspects of pragmatics. It is known that pragmatic analysis involves the study of ways of expression of content. However, this content is not based on the formal indicators of lexical and syntactic units, but on the use of speech structures in a certain context. Philosopher J. Austin and his follower J. Searle proposed to use the concept of "speech act" in relation to the activation of structures in connection with such a context. According to their interpretation, logicians and linguists somewhat forget the performative aspect of language use. In fact, they do not simply speak, but perform some action or task by speaking.

According to the founders of the theory of speech acts, the persons pronouncing the sentence perform actions such as informing, asking, ordering, requesting, and promising. As a result, "in all areas of linguistics, the issues of speech acts were considered as a product of the interaction-intervention process, separated as a speech event, it was emphasized that it is a unit representing the communicative purpose of the author of the speech, and it was studied as an implicit structure of speech and text."

In speech acts, the content can have an explicit expression in addition to the implicit expression. For example, in the structure I ask you to come to the University this afternoon, the content of the request is openly expressed by means of the performative verb to ask. But this is not a common situation. In plural cases, the content of the same speech act is expressed

using different syntactic forms. Moreover, speech acts are usually related to syntactic and semantic categories, and therefore, when performing the speech act of request, we can refer to various syntactic devices (Buzrukova 2021). At the same time, a syntactic structure made with the participation of a single verb can express different illocutionary content. So, researchers are busy searching for the classification signs of speech acts and determining what tools and mechanisms speakers use to express this or that content (Vezhbitska 1986; Bogdanov 1989; Bach 2003).

As noted by I.P. Susov, the structure of each sentence consists of two parts, one of which serves to show the proposition, and the other refers to the illocutionary force or pragmatic task. In addition to the inflectional forms of the verb and the performative verb, word order, stress, intonation, etc. indicate the task being performed. In addition, the illocutionary function can be determined based on the context. For example, hanging the inscription "Zlaya sobaka" in Russian on the gate serves as a warning speech act.

The German scientist K. Bach proposes to classify speech acts based on the meaning of the verb. In this classification, in addition to the attitude expressed by the speaker, the attitude of the listener is also taken into account. In this regard, four classes of speech acts are distinguished:

The classifications proposed by K. Bach and other linguists, of course, have their place in the development of the theory of speech acts, and they have been tested in a number of studies. But linguistic categories are constantly activated in connection with one or the other, and the range of speech actions performed during linguistic activity is wide. The recommended classifications are based on three criteria. These are state of mind, appropriateness of situation and point of illocution. "When relying on other criteria, - concludes J. Verschuren (for example, the relationship between the speaker and the listener, such as the difference between asking and ordering) the classification looks different."

J. May, a well-known representative of the field of pragmalinguistics, observes that it is difficult to apply the theory of speech acts to the study of units above the sentence (for example, speech cluster), uses the concept of pragmatic act (pragmatic act) and approves its use in speech cluster or text analysis. Pragmatic act consists of micro and macro speech acts. In other words, the concept of pragmatic act makes it possible to have information about the content of the sentence and the higher levels.

Pragmalinguists, while thinking about linguistic choice and its appropriateness to the situation, note that there are three ways to ensure the alternative choice of linguistic means. The first of these relies on the possible presuppositions in this or that choice. The second is the formation of conditions that coordinate the choice that occurs in the case of speech implicature. Thirdly, it is taken into account that the speech act sounds appropriate only in certain situations. In all of the listed cases, it is possible to talk about the correspondence of the macro speech act to the linguistic, psychological and cultural world of the speaking person.

Van Dijk emphasized that the work of art should be viewed as a speech act with its own adaptation conditions. He recommends distinguishing between macro- and micro-speech acts in artistic works. If the macro-speech act is a whole text, the micro-acts, in turn, occur through the sentence in the text. It is known that information is expressed not only at the level of sentences, but also through the medium of discourse, which is formed by the interconnection of sentences. Because the principles that form discourse structures are activated precisely in

the discourse structure. It is not a general rule that macro speech acts consist of specific speech acts. On the contrary, they cannot avoid actions related to controlling the adaptation of speech acts to the environment.

In this example, we do not find performative verbs or other grammatical forms that openly express speech acts such as "to offer", "to request", "to ask", "to indicate". Teacher Duyshen has only one goal: he loves his student Altinoy and is looking for a way to express his love. His speech is implicit and the implied pragmatic content can only be understood through context. Here, the scope of the context includes the topic under discussion, the communication situation, and the surrounding conditions. It should be taken into account that the content that comes from the original purpose of the speaker, relying on the presuppositions about the subject and previous circumstances, reaches the reader of the work. Scholars who have recognized that "a presupposition is a sum of pre-known knowledge that allows for the correct application and correct understanding of a certain sentence" note that it includes context and situation, and the presupposition can be known to the speaker or, at least, can be determined by logical analysis of the proposition in the text. they emphasize (Hakimov, Gazieva 2020: 98-99).

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